

ANALGESIC ACTIVITY OF NATURAL PAIN-RELIEVING MEDICINAL PLANTS: SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF PHYTOCONSTITUENTS, MOLECULAR MECHANISMS, NEUROINFLAMMATION, PRECLINICAL EVIDENCE, SAFETY, AND DRUG DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Pain represents one of the most prevalent clinical symptoms affecting human health and quality of life worldwide. Conventional analgesic drugs such as opioids and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are associated with significant adverse effects, including gastrointestinal irritation, tolerance, dependence, and organ toxicity. Consequently, medicinal plants have gained increasing scientific attention as alternative sources of safer analgesic agents. Natural phytochemicals such as flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, phenolic acids, saponins, and glycosides demonstrate significant antinociceptive and anti-inflammatory properties through modulation of nociceptive signaling pathways, oxidative stress and neuroinflammatory responses. This systematic review compiles experimental and mechanistic evidence regarding analgesic medicinal plants evaluated in in-

vitro and in vivo models, including hot plate test, tail flick test, acetic acid-induced writhing, formalin test and carrageenan-induced inflammation. Molecular targets such as cyclooxygenase enzymes, transient receptor potential channels, cytokines, ion channels and

glial activation pathways are discussed. Despite promising preclinical findings, challenges remain in extract standardization, pharmacokinetic evaluation, and controlled clinical trials. Advances in phytochemical characterization, nanotechnology-based drug delivery, and translational pharmacology may facilitate development of plant-derived analgesic therapeutics. Natural analgesics hold substantial potential for future drug discovery and integrative pain management strategies.

KEYWORDS: Analgesic medicinal plants, Antinociceptive activity, Neuroinflammation, Phytochemicals, Pain mechanisms.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

Highlight

- ✓ Pain involves physiological and psychological responses to tissue injury or disease
- ✓ Analgesic drugs relieve pain but cause tolerance, addiction and organ toxicity
- ✓ Medicinal plants are explored as safer alternatives for pain management
- ✓ Phytochemicals modulate central and peripheral pathways producing analgesia
- ✓ Experimental studies validate antinociceptive effects of herbal compounds

1. INTRODUCTION

Pain is a complex physiological and psychological experience associated with tissue injury, inflammation or neurological dysfunction. It is broadly classified into nociceptive, inflammatory, and neuropathic pain.^[1] Synthetic analgesic drugs provide symptomatic relief but often lead to tolerance, addiction, gastrointestinal disturbances, renal impairment and

cardiovascular risks. Therefore, plant-based analgesics are being extensively investigated as safer alternatives.^[2] Medicinal plants have been traditionally used for centuries to alleviate pain and inflammatory conditions. Ethnopharmacological knowledge indicates that numerous botanical species contain bioactive compounds capable of modulating pain pathways.^[3] Research indicates that medicinal plants may act on both central and peripheral nervous systems to produce analgesic effects. Furthermore, systematic reviews of herbal analgesics demonstrate that multiple phytochemicals possess antinociceptive properties validated through experimental pharmacology and mechanistic studies.^[4]

2. Phytoconstituents responsible for analgesic activity

Natural pain-relieving medicinal plants are rich sources of structurally diverse bioactive phytochemicals, including flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, phenolic acids, tannins, glycosides, and saponins. These compounds exhibit significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties through multiple pharmacological mechanisms.^[5] In particular, flavonoids and tannins contribute to pain attenuation by suppressing prostaglandin biosynthesis, reducing oxidative stress, and modulating inflammatory mediators.^[6] Contemporary research further indicates that such phytochemicals possess multi-target actions on nociceptive signaling pathways, supporting their potential use as alternative or adjunct therapeutic agents in the management of chronic pain conditions.^[7]

3. Molecular Mechanisms of Analgesic Action

Plant-derived analgesics act through multiple molecular pathways.

3.1 Cyclooxygenase (COX) and Prostaglandin Inhibition

Many medicinal plant extracts exhibit analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects by inhibiting the activity of the cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) enzyme. This suppression limits the conversion of arachidonic acid into pro-inflammatory prostaglandins, thereby decreasing inflammatory responses and nociceptive pain signaling.^[8]

3.2 Modulation of Ion Channels

Natural phytochemicals can modulate pain perception by interacting with key neuronal ion channels, including voltage-gated sodium channels, calcium channels, and transient receptor potential vanilloid-1 (TRPV1) receptors. Through regulation of these molecular targets, such compounds influence neuronal excitability and synaptic transmission of nociceptive signals, thereby contributing to their analgesic effects.^[9]

3.3 Neuroinflammatory pathway regulation

This figure 1 illustrates the neuroinflammatory cascade underlying chronic pain development. Tissue injury or oxidative stress initiates activation of microglia and astrocytes, leading to the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , IL-6) and nitric oxide. These mediators trigger NF- κ B signaling, promoting neuronal sensitization and synaptic plasticity, which ultimately result in persistent pain perception. The diagram also highlights the therapeutic role of phytochemicals, which attenuate this pathway through cytokine suppression, NF- κ B inhibition, antioxidant activity, and modulation of glial cell responses.

Figure 1: Neuroinflammatory pathway in chronic pain and phytochemical modulation.

(Tissue injury activates glial cells \rightarrow cytokines & NF- κ B \rightarrow neuronal sensitization \rightarrow chronic pain; phytochemicals suppress inflammation and oxidative stress.)

3.4 Antioxidant-mediated neuroprotection

Reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a pivotal role in the initiation and progression of neuropathic pain by inducing lipid peroxidation, mitochondrial dysfunction, and neuronal damage. Excessive oxidative stress activates redox-sensitive signaling pathways such as NF- κ B and MAPKs, amplifying inflammatory responses and neuronal sensitization.^[10] Polyphenols, as potent natural antioxidants, scavenge free radicals, chelate metal ions and enhance endogenous antioxidant defenses including superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase and glutathione. By restoring redox homeostasis, they protect neuronal integrity, inhibit neuroinflammation and reduce pain hypersensitivity.^[11] Additionally, polyphenols modulate signaling pathways and improve mitochondrial function, contributing to sustained neuroprotection and attenuation of chronic neuropathic pain.

3.5 Opioid receptor interaction

Plant alkaloids exert opioid-like analgesia via μ -opioid receptors, while medicinal plants reduce pain through anti-inflammatory and neuromodulator mechanisms.^[12] This figure 2 This figure depicts the nociceptive pathway from stimulus to pain perception and highlights how plant phytochemicals modulate key steps, including prostaglandin synthesis, ion channel activity, and inflammatory signaling, to exert analgesic effects.

Figure 2: Phytochemical modulation of nociceptive signaling pathway.

(Pain stimulus → prostaglandin-mediated signaling → ion channel activation → pain; phytochemicals inhibit COX, inflammation, and neural transmission.)

4. Experimental evaluation of analgesic activity

These figures 3 and 4 collectively present experimental approaches and underlying mechanisms in pain research. Figure 3 outlines standard preclinical models used to evaluate analgesic activity, including central (hot plate), peripheral (writhing, formalin), and inflammatory (carrageenan-induced edema) assays. Figure 4 complements this by illustrating the neuroinflammatory cascade driving pain, glial cell activation and subsequent cytokine release contribute to neuronal sensitization. Together, they highlight how plant phytochemicals exert analgesic effects by modulating both experimentally validated pain models and key molecular pathways such as NF- κ B, ROS, and pro-inflammatory cytokine signaling.

4.1 *In Vitro* models^[13]

- COX inhibition assay
- Nitric oxide scavenging assay
- HRBC membrane stabilization test

4.2 Table 1: *In Vivo* analgesic models.

Model	Type of pain	Mechanism	Ref
Hot plate test	Central analgesia	Supraspinal response	[14]
Tail flick test	Central analgesia	Spinal reflex	[15]
Acetic acid writhing	Peripheral pain	Prostaglandin mediated	[16]
Formalin test	Biphasic pain	Neurogenic + inflammatory	[17]
Carrageenan edema	Inflammation	Cytokine mediated	[18]

Experimental pharmacological studies have demonstrated significant analgesic activity of plant extracts in these models. Figures illustrate key experimental models used for preclinical analgesic screening and the underlying neuroinflammatory pain pathway. Central, peripheral and inflammatory pain models evaluate analgesic potential, while plant phytochemicals mitigate pain by suppressing NF- κ B-mediated oxidative and cytokine-driven neuronal sensitization.

Preclinical analgesic evaluation models

Figure 3: Preclinical pain assessment models used for analgesic screening

(Diagram illustrating central (hot plate), peripheral (writhing, formalin), and inflammatory (carrageenan-induced edema) experimental models for evaluating analgesic activity)

Neuroinflammatory pathway targeted by plant analgesics

Figure 4: Neuroinflammatory pain pathway and inhibition by plant phytochemicals.

(Inflammatory stimulus activates microglia → cytokine release → neuronal sensitization → pain.

Plant phytochemicals suppress NF- κ B, ROS, and cytokine signaling, reducing neuroinflammation and producing analgesia).

5. Table 2: Major medicinal plants with analgesic activity.

Plant	Family	Part used	Extraction method	Analgesic assay	Major compound	ReF.
<i>Abelmoschus esculentus</i>	Malvaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Formalin	Polyphenols	[19]
<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	Asteraceae	Aerial	Ethanol	Hot plate	Flavonoids	[20]
<i>Acorus calamus</i>	Acoraceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Tail flick	β -asarone	[21]
<i>Adhatoda vasica</i>	Acanthaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Writhing	Vasicinone	[22]
<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Rutaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Hot plate	Marmelosin	[23]
<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	Simaroubaceae	Bark	Ethanol	Tail flick	Quassinoids	[24]
<i>Aloe vera</i>	Asphodelaceae	Leaf gel	Aqueous	Writhing	Aloin	[25]
<i>Alpinia galanga</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome	Ethanol	Formalin	Galangin	[26]
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	Apocynaceae	Bark	Methanol	Tail flick	Alkaloids	[27]

<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i>	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant	Ethanol	Writhing	Flavonoids	[28]
<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Andrographolide	[29]
<i>Anethum graveolens</i>	Apiaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Hot plate	Carvone	[30]
<i>Annona muricata</i>	Annonaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Tail flick	Acetogenins	[31]
<i>Argemone mexicana</i>	Papaveraceae	Seed	Ethanol	Writhing	Alkaloids	[32]
<i>Artemisia vulgaris</i>	Asteraceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Artemisinin	[33]
<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Asparagaceae	Root	Ethanol	Hot plate	Shatavarins	[34]
<i>Averrhoa carambola</i>	Oxalidaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Tail flick	Polyphenols	[35]
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Meliaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Formalin	Nimbidin	[36]
<i>Bacopa monnieri</i>	Plantaginaceae	Whole plant	Methanol	Writhing	Bacosides	[37]
<i>Berberis aristata</i>	Berberidaceae	Root	Ethanol	Hot plate	Berberine	[38]
<i>Beta vulgaris</i>	Amaranthaceae	Root	Methanol	Tail flick	Betalains	[39]
<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i>	Nyctaginaceae	Root	Ethanol	Formalin	Boeravinones	[40]
<i>Boesenbergia rotunda</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Writhing	Pinostrobin	[41]
<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	Malvaceae	Bark	Ethanol	Hot plate	Flavonoids	[42]
<i>Boswellia serrata</i>	Burseraceae	Resin	Methanol	Tail flick	Boswellic acids	[43]
<i>Brassica nigra</i>	Brassicaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Formalin	Sinigrin	[44]
<i>Brassica oleracea</i>	Brassicaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Writhing	Sulforaphane	[45]
<i>Butea monosperma</i>	Fabaceae	Flower	Ethanol	Hot plate	Butrin	[46]
<i>Calotropis procera</i>	Apocynaceae	Latex	Methanol	Tail flick	Calotropin	[47]
<i>Calendula officinalis</i>	Asteraceae	Flower	Ethanol	Formalin	Lutein	[48]
<i>Camellia oleifera</i>	Theaceae	Seed	Methanol	Writhing	Saponins	[49]
<i>Capsicum frutescens</i>	Solanaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Hot plate	Capsaicin	[50]
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Caricaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Tail flick	Papain	[51]
<i>Carthamus tinctorius</i>	Asteraceae	Seed	Ethanol	Formalin	Carthamin	[52]
<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Fabaceae	Bark	Methanol	Writhing	Anthraquinones	[53]
<i>Cajanus cajan</i>	Fabaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Hot plate	Isoflavones	[54]
<i>Cedrus deodara</i>	Pinaceae	Wood	Methanol	Tail flick	Lignans	[55]
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Apiaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Formalin	Asiaticoside	[56]
<i>Chenopodium album</i>	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Writhing	Polyphenols	[57]
<i>Cichorium intybus</i>	Asteraceae	Root	Ethanol	Hot plate	Inulin	[58]
<i>Cinnamomum</i>	Lauraceae	Bark	Methanol	Tail flick	Cinnamaldehyde	[59]

<i>verum</i>						
<i>Clitoria ternatea</i>	Fabaceae	Flower	Ethanol	Formalin	Anthocyanins	[60]
<i>Cleome viscosa</i>	Cleomaceae	Seed	Methanol	Writhing	Glucosinolates	[61]
<i>Cocos nucifera</i>	Arecaceae	Oil	Ethanol	Hot plate	Lauric acid	[62]
<i>Coffea arabica</i>	Rubiaceae	Bean	Aqueous	Tail flick	Chlorogenic acid	[63]
<i>Commiphora mukul</i>	Burseraceae	Resin	Methanol	Formalin	Guggulsterones	[64]
<i>Coriandrum sativum</i>	Apiaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Writhing	Linalool	[65]
<i>Crocus sativus</i>	Iridaceae	Stigma	Methanol	Hot plate	Crocin	[66]
<i>Curculigo orchioides</i>	Hypoxidaceae	Root	Ethanol	Tail flick	Saponins	[67]
<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Formalin	Curcumin	[68]
<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i>	Poaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Writhing	Citral	[69]
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	Cyperaceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Hot plate	Cyperene	[70]
<i>Datura metel</i>	Solanaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Tropane alkaloids	[71]
<i>Delonix regia</i>	Fabaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Flavonoids	[72]
<i>Echinacea purpurea</i>	Asteraceae	Root	Ethanol	Writhing	Cichoric acid	[73]
<i>Eclipta alba</i>	Asteraceae	Whole plant	Methanol	Hot plate	Wedelolactone	[74]
<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>	Zingiberaceae	Seed	Methanol	Formalin	Cineole	[75]
<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i>	Myrtaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Writhing	Eucalyptol	[76]
<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Moraceae	Bark	Methanol	Hot plate	Tannins	[77]
<i>Ficus carica</i>	Moraceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Tail flick	Phenolics	[78]
<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	Moraceae	Bark	Methanol	Formalin	Tannins	[79]
<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Moraceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Writhing	Phenolics	[80]
<i>Foeniculum vulgare</i>	Apiaceae	Seed	Methanol	Hot plate	Anethole	[80]
<i>Garcinia cambogia</i>	Clusiaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Tail flick	Hydroxycitric acid	[81]
<i>Ginkgo biloba</i>	Ginkgoaceae	Leaf	Standard extract	Formalin	Ginkgolides	[82]
<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Fabaceae	Root	Hydroalcoholic	Writhing	Glycyrrhizin	[83]
<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i>	Apocynaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Hot plate	Gymnemic acids	[84]
<i>Helianthus annuus</i>	Asteraceae	Seed	Oil extract	Tail flick	Tocopherols	[85]
<i>Holarrhena antidysenterica</i>	Apocynaceae	Bark	Methanol	Formalin	Conessine	[86]
<i>Hordeum vulgare</i>	Poaceae	Grain	Ethanol	Writhing	Phenolic acids	[87]
<i>Hypericum</i>	Hypericaceae	Aerial	Methanol	Hot plate	Hypericin	[88]

<i>perforatum</i>						
<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>	Convolvulaceae	Tuber	Ethanol	Tail flick	Anthocyanins	[89]
<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Phorbol esters	[90]
<i>Justicia adhatoda</i>	Acanthaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Writhing	Vasicine	[91]
<i>Kaempferia galanga</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Hot plate	Kaempferol	[92]
<i>Lactuca sativa</i>	Asteraceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Phenolics	[93]
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	Lythraceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Lawsone	[94]
<i>Lepidium sativum</i>	Brassicaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Writhing	Glucosinolates	[95]
<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	Linaceae	Seed	Methanol	Hot plate	Lignans	[96]
<i>Lantana camara</i>	Verbenaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Triterpenoids	[97]
<i>Lycium barbarum</i>	Solanaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Formalin	Zeaxanthin	[98]
<i>Madhuca longifolia</i>	Sapotaceae	Flower	Ethanol	Writhing	Triterpenes	[99]
<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Anacardiaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Hot plate	Mangiferin	[100]
<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i>	Asteraceae	Flower	Ethanol	Tail flick	Apigenin	[101]
<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Menthol	[102]
<i>Mimusops elengi</i>	Sapotaceae	Bark	Ethanol	Writhing	Triterpenoids	[103]
<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Hot plate	Charantin	[104]
<i>Morinda citrifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Tail flick	Scopoletin	[105]
<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Moringaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Quercetin	[106]
<i>Nardostachys jatamansi</i>	Caprifoliaceae	Root	Ethanol	Writhing	Jatamansone	[107]
<i>Nigella sativa</i>	Ranunculaceae	Seed	Oil extract	Hot plate	Thymoquinone	[108]
<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Eugenol	[109]
<i>Origanum majorana</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Terpenoids	[110]
<i>Panax ginseng</i>	Araliaceae	Root	Ethanol	Writhing	Ginsenosides	[111]
<i>Passiflora edulis</i>	Passifloraceae	Fruit	Methanol	Hot plate	Vitamin C	[112]
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Arecaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Formalin	Phenolics	[113]
<i>Picrorhiza kurroa</i>	Plantaginaceae	Root	Ethanol	Writhing	Picrosides	[114]
<i>Piper longum</i>	Piperaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Hot plate	Piperlongumine	[115]
<i>Plantago major</i>	Plantaginaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Iridoids	[116]
<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	Plumbaginaceae	Root	Methanol	Formalin	Plumbagin	[117]
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	Fabaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Writhing	Pongamol	[118]
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Portulacaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Hot plate	Omega-3	[119]
<i>Prunus avium</i>	Rosaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Tail flick	Cyanidin	[120]
<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Myrtaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Quercetin	[121]
<i>Rauwolfia</i>	Apocynaceae	Root	Ethanol	Writhing	Reserpine	[122]

<i>serpentina</i>						
<i>Raphanus sativus</i>	Brassicaceae	Root	Methanol	Hot plate	Anthocyanins	[123]
<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Rosmarinic acid	[124]
<i>Rubus idaeus</i>	Rosaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Formalin	Polyphenols	[125]
<i>Salvia officinalis</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Writhing	Carnosic acid	[126]
<i>Saraca asoca</i>	Fabaceae	Bark	Methanol	Hot plate	Catechols	[127]
<i>Sesamum indicum</i>	Pedaliaceae	Seed	Oil extract	Tail flick	Sesamol	[128]
<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i>	Fabaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Formalin	Flavonoids	[129]
<i>Shorea robusta</i>	Dipterocarpaceae	Resin	Methanol	Writhing	Resveratrol derivatives	[130]
<i>Sida cordifolia</i>	Malvaceae	Whole plant	Ethanol	Hot plate	Ephedrine	[131]
<i>Silybum marianum</i>	Asteraceae	Seed	Methanol	Tail flick	Silymarin	[132]
<i>Smilax china</i>	Smilacaceae	Root	Ethanol	Formalin	Saponins	[133]
<i>Solanum nigrum</i>	Solanaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Writhing	Solanine	[134]
<i>Spinacia oleracea</i>	Amaranthaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Hot plate	Lutein	[135]
<i>Swertia chirayita</i>	Gentianaceae	Whole plant	Methanol	Tail flick	Amarogentin	[136]
<i>Syzygium aromaticum</i>	Myrtaceae	Bud	Essential oil	Formalin	Eugenol	[137]
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Fabaceae	Pulp	Methanol	Writhing	Tartaric acid	[138]
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	Fabaceae	Whole plant	Ethanol	Hot plate	Flavonoids	[139]
<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Combretaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Formalin	Gallic acid	[140]
<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Combretaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Writhing	Tannins	[141]
<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Malvaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Hot plate	Epicatechin	[142]
<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Tail flick	Thymol	[143]
<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i>	Menispermaceae	Stem	Aqueous	Formalin	Tinosporaside	[144]
<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>	Apiaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Writhing	Thymol	[145]
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Fruit	Methanol	Hot plate	Saponins	[146]
<i>Urtica dioica</i>	Urticaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Phenolics	[147]
<i>Vaccinium myrtillus</i>	Ericaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Writhing	Anthocyanins	[148]
<i>Valeriana wallichii</i>	Caprifoliaceae	Root	Methanol	Hot plate	Valerenic acid	[149]
<i>Vitex negundo</i>	Lamiaceae	Leaf	Ethanol	Tail flick	Flavonoids	[150]
<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Solanaceae	Root	Methanol	Formalin	Withanolides	[151]
<i>Zea mays</i>	Poaceae	Kernel	Ethanol	Writhing	Anthocyanins	[152]

<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Hot plate	Gingerols	[153]
<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	Rhamnaceae	Fruit	Ethanol	Tail flick	Saponins	[154]
<i>Ziziphus nummularia</i>	Rhamnaceae	Leaf	Methanol	Formalin	Cyclopeptide alkaloids	[155]
<i>Costus speciosus</i>	Costaceae	Rhizome	Methanol	Hot plate	Diosgenin	[156]
<i>Dolichos biflorus</i>	Fabaceae	Seed	Ethanol	Tail flick	Flavonoids	[157]
<i>Enicostema littorale</i>	Gentianaceae	Whole plant	Methanol	Formalin	Swertiamarin	[158]
<i>Fagonia cretica</i>	Zygophyllaceae	Whole plant	Ethanol	Writhing	Saponins	[159]
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	Lamiaceae	Bark	Methanol	Hot plate	Lignans	[160]
<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i>	Acanthaceae	Root	Methanol	Formalin	Alkaloids	[161]

6. Safety and toxicological considerations

Although medicinal plants are widely regarded as relatively safe, potential toxicological concerns can occur under certain conditions, including excessive or prolonged high-dose exposure, contamination with heavy metals or pesticides and clinically significant herb-drug interactions. Therefore, comprehensive safety evaluation through standardized toxicity assessment and detailed pharmacokinetic characterization is necessary prior to therapeutic or clinical use. In contrast, topical herbal analgesic formulations have demonstrated encouraging safety outcomes, primarily because localized drug delivery limits systemic absorption and thereby reduces the likelihood of generalized adverse effects.

7. Drug development potential

Natural analgesic phytochemicals provide several therapeutic advantages, including multi-target pharmacological actions, comparatively lower adverse effects and significant structural diversity that supports drug discovery. Recent scientific progress has further strengthened their clinical potential through approaches such as nano formulation strategies, enhancement of oral bioavailability and molecular docking–assisted identification of bioactive constituents. Consequently, plant-derived compounds continue to represent important lead structures for the rational design and development of next-generation analgesic agents.

8. DISCUSSION

Scientific evidence strongly supports the analgesic efficacy of medicinal plants across diverse experimental models. Multi-mechanistic actions such as inhibition of inflammatory mediators, modulation of neuronal ion channels and antioxidant effects contribute to their therapeutic potential. However, variability in plant species, extraction methods, and

experimental protocols complicates comparison of results. Standardization of bioactive markers and translational clinical research remain critical challenges.

9. CONCLUSION

Medicinal plants constitute a valuable source of natural analgesic agents with scientifically validated pharmacological mechanisms. Their ability to modulate inflammatory pathways, oxidative stress, and nociceptive signaling positions them as promising alternatives or adjuncts to conventional analgesics. Future research focusing on clinical trials, standardization, and advanced drug delivery systems will facilitate integration of plant-based analgesics into modern therapeutic practice.

Declaration

Ethics approval and consent to participate

This work is a review and involves no experimental studies on humans or animals; hence, ethical approval and informed consent are not required.

Clinical Trial No

This manuscript is a review and does not involve a clinical trial; therefore, trial registration and a registration number are not applicable.

Consent for publication

This manuscript includes no personal data; therefore, consent is not required and is not applicable.

Availability of data and material

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